

Adjusting expected goals (xG) and shots on target for game context in soccer

Andrey Skripnikov*, Ahmet Cemek, David Gillman

Natural Sciences Division, New College of Florida

Abstract

With advancements in soccer analytics, considerable attention has been devoted to developing sophisticated measures for quality scoring opportunities —such as expected goals and expected threat. Far less effort, however, has gone toward adjusting these and other performance metrics for game context, including factors like score differential, red cards, and time remaining. It is well known that certain match scenarios prompt systematic tactical adjustments—for example, teams often defend more conservatively when leading or playing shorthanded. In this study, we employ generalized additive mixed-effects models (GAMMs) on minute-by-minute match event data from Europe’s five major leagues to quantify how such contextual variables influence offensive production metrics like shots on target and expected goals. This approach allows us to estimate global effects of contextual variables on offensive production, while also allowing for league-specific distinctions to be captured via random effects. We then use these estimates to adjust observed team statistics, projecting each team’s performance onto a standardized baseline scenario—a tied home game played at even manpower. We believe the resulting adjusted measures to better isolate underlying team quality by removing distortions arising from transient tactical responses to game state.

Keywords. Generalized Additive Models, Mixed-Effects Models, Negative Binomial, Soccer Analytics, Tweedie

*Corresponding author

1 Introduction

Soccer performance metrics are often interpreted without accounting for the tactical context in which they are generated. For example, teams leading in score may deliberately cede possession, while teams trailing may press forward aggressively, creating substantial biases in raw totals of shots or other statistics. In our earlier work [1], we developed an adjustment framework to account for such factors when interpreting shot attempts and corner kicks. By projecting observed offensive outputs onto a standardized baseline game state, we demonstrated that contextual adjustments yield statistics more consistent with intuitive measures of performance such as league standings, while also improving forecasting performance when used as predictive features.

In this study, we extend that approach to two widely used modern metrics: *expected goals* (xG) and *shots on target*. xG in particular has become a central tool in soccer analytics [2, 3], quantifying shot quality by incorporating shot distance, angle, and other contextual features. Related approaches in other sports—such as expected goals in hockey [4], expected possession value in rugby [5], or expected points in American football [6]—highlight the broad value of probabilistic performance measures. However, relatively few studies attempt to adjust these advanced statistics for in-game context such as score differential or red cards, despite the well-documented impact of such context on team’s tactical behavior.

This paper differs from our earlier work in several key respects. First, data availability was more limited, with xG and shots on target being only obtainable from *fbref.com* [2] beginning in 2017/18 season. Second, because xG is continuous and zero-inflated at the minute level, we considered Gaussian and Tweedie [7] response models to accommodate it. That is in contrast to utilizing Poisson-family approaches in our previous work that focused on count-based data such as shot attempts and corner kicks (granted, we still use those Poisson-family approaches here to model the shots on target, due to their count nature). Lastly, rather than estimating separate models for each league, we adopted a unified cross-league framework with random effects, yielding both global and league-specific estimates. This allows us to present a robust global adjustment that can be applied across competitions, while still acknowledging between-league variability.

2 Methods

2.1 Data Collection

We compiled minute-by-minute data from 2017–2023 for five major European leagues: Premier League, La Liga, Bundesliga, Ligue 1, and Serie A. From *fbref.com* [2], we obtained expected goals (xG) and shots on target, while red card events were extracted from *ESPN.com* game text commentary. Pre-match betting odds were collected from *Oddsportal.com* and converted into win probability differentials, serving as a measure of relative team strength [8]. The final data format resulted in two observations (one for each team) per any given minute of the game, where we reflect the score and red card differential as of that minute, the xG and shots on target each respective team accumulated within that minute, alongside the prematch betting coefficients and home/away status of each team.

To reduce instability at distributional extremes, which tended to result from low sample size of available data at those extremes, we did as follows: score differentials of ≤ -3 and $\geq +3$ were treated as -3 and $+3$, respectively, and red card differentials of ≤ -2 and $\geq +2$ were treated as -2 and $+2$, respectively. Game minute was reset at halftime, with half indicator utilized in order to distinguish between the halves of play. Each minute of extra time beyond 45 minutes within a half was treated the same as minute 45. The latter helped curtail issues arising due to game-to-game volatility of the amount of time that was getting added at the end of halves, instead treating all the observations from 45th minute onward equally.

2.2 Modeling Framework

We modeled minute-level outputs (xG or shots on target) using generalized additive models (GAMs) [9], which flexibly capture nonlinear relationships between outcomes and contextual covariates, while also allowing for seamless interpretation and statistical inference. Candidate distributions included Gaussian, Tweedie (to handle excess zeros in xG), and Poisson-family models for comparison. In particular, for modeling continuous variable xG, we considered Gaussian with identity and log links, and Tweedie with log and inverse links. To model the count variable of shots on target, we compared Poisson-family models (regular Poisson, Negative Binomial and Zero-Inflated

Poisson) and Gaussian models (identity and log link).

The unified model encompassing all five leagues under consideration was specified as (on the example of xG):

$$\begin{aligned} \log(xG) \sim & s(S.Diff) + s(S.Diff, \text{by}=\text{League}, \mathbf{re}) + \\ & s(RC.Diff) + s(RC.Diff, \text{by}=\text{League}, \mathbf{re}) + \\ & Home + s(WP.Diff) + \\ & s(GM \mid Half = 1) + s(GM \mid Half = 2) + \\ & s(Team, \mathbf{re}) + s(League, \mathbf{re}) + s(season, \mathbf{re}), \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

Here, $s(S.Diff)$ and $s(RC.Diff)$ represent the smooth nonlinear global effects of score and red card differential, respectively; league-specific deviations from those global effects are captured via factor-smooth random interaction effects $s(S.Diff, \text{by}=\text{League}, \mathbf{re})$ and $s(RC.Diff, \text{by}=\text{League}, \mathbf{re})$, which can get shrunk towards zero via a penalty; $Home$ is a binary indicator for home advantage; $s(WP.Diff)$ controls for relative team strength based on pre-match odds (the "win probability differential"); $s(GM \mid Half = 1)$ and $s(GM \mid Half = 2)$ allow separate time effects for each half; random intercepts $s(Team, \mathbf{re})$, $s(League, \mathbf{re})$, and $s(season, \mathbf{re})$ capture heterogeneity at team, league, and season levels.

This specification simultaneously estimates global effects (averaging across leagues) and league-specific adjustments, with the global estimates emphasized for subsequent use due to their greater stability.

2.3 Model Selection

When selecting the most appropriate model, we leveraged DHARMa [10] for goodness-of-fit testing. It provided quantile-quantile and residuals-vs-fitted plots, along with a handful of diagnostic tests (Kolmogorov-Smirnov uniformity test, outlier test, overdispersion and zero-inflation tests). Due to xG being continuous and zero-inflated at the minute level, we considered Gaussian

and Tweedie response models. For shots on target, we stuck with the Poisson-family approaches much like in our previous work [1] .

2.4 Adjustment Procedure

The adjustment procedure follows the principle of projecting observed outcomes onto a standardized baseline game state: a tied home game played at even strength (hence, both the score and red card differentials are equal to 0). Let $\eta(S.Diff, RC.diff, Home)$ denote the estimated linear predictor for a given score differential $S.Diff$, red card differential $RC.Diff$, and home/away status. If a team records Y units of xG or shots on target in that state, given the log link used for the response variable, the adjusted equivalent under the baseline state ($S.Diff = 0, RC.Diff = 0, Home = 1$) is:

$$Y^* = Y \cdot \exp(\eta(0, 0, 1) - \eta(S.Diff, RC.Diff, Home)).$$

This transformation inverts the contextual effect, rescaling observed performance to what would be expected in the baseline scenario. Adjustments are applied multiplicatively on the response scale, with uncertainty quantified using the posterior covariance of GAMM parameter estimates to generate confidence intervals.

No adjustment is applied for win probability differential or game minute, as these reflect inherent team strength and match timing rather than tactical asymmetries. Instead, they are included in the model simply to control for confounding.

2.5 Forecasting performance testing

To assess whether our adjustments improve predictive accuracy, we evaluated their performance in forecasting score differentials using a multiple linear regression model. The model included the home and away teams' statistic values (e.g., shots per game to date) as predictors, with the home team's final score differential as the response. For each season, we trained the model on the first 50% of games (≈ 190 total, or ≈ 19 per team) and tested on the remaining 50%. Per-game averages were computed only from the training data to prevent data leakage. Forecasting per-

formance was measured by root mean squared error (RMSE), comparing models using adjusted versus raw statistics. For each metric (xG and shots on target), we performed a paired t -test on RMSE differences - comparing the adjusted versus unadjusted forecasting performance for each league-season combination in order to see if the mean improvement was significant.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Nature of Estimated Effects

After having considered Gaussian and Tweedie models for xG, and several Poisson-family and Gaussian models for shots on target, we landed on log-link Tweedie for xG and Negative Binomial for shots on target, respectively. These models showcased the best goodness-of-fit performance according to DHARMA diagnostics (see the supplement for details).

On Figure 1 we introduce the nature of effects that score and red card differential have on expected goals and shots on target, respectively. Those effect displays were generated as predictions of per-minute rates from the log-link Tweedie (xG) and Negative Binomial (shots on target) GAMM.

Judging by the global effect, one can witness a monotonic negative trend for both the score and red card differentials, which aligns with the intuition. When teams trail in score, they tend to play more offensively, naturally resulting in more shots on target. Conversely, teams leading in score start prioritizing defense in an effort to protect the lead, hence sacrificing some of the offensive production. Same logic also holds for the expected goals, although not to as strong of a degree as showcased by a slightly flatter pattern. That could be intuitively explained by the fact that, when your opponent plays more defensively, you can still generate shots on target, but producing actual high-quality shots (with high xG) is not as easy due to the likely increase in the number of defenders between the attacker and the goal.

As for the red card differential effect, it is a rather predictable decrease in volume and quality of scoring opportunities for teams playing with fewer men, i.e. more red cards. Playing short-handed virtually always forces a team into a more defensive playing style simply due to lack of manpower.

Figure 1: Nature of effects for score differential, red card differential, win probability differential and game minute in 1st/2nd halves on shot attempts (left) and corner kicks (right) in the baseline Negative Binomial Generalized Additive smoothing splines model fitted to 15 seasons (2008-2023) across five major European soccer leagues, along with the global effect (averaged over those five leagues). The y-axis is on the scale of linear predictor (log-response). The extreme predictor values (± 3 for score differential, ± 2 for red card differential, 45+ for minute) were binned.

Score Diff	Expected Goals (xG)	Shots On Target
-3	0.88 [0.82, 0.95]	0.84 [0.79, 0.90]
-2	0.86 [0.82, 0.91]	0.83 [0.79, 0.88]
-1	0.90 [0.87, 0.93]	0.86 [0.85, 0.91]
+1	1.10 [1.07, 1.14]	1.25 [1.20, 1.29]
+2	1.11 [1.06, 1.17]	1.32 [1.25, 1.39]
+3	1.12 [1.05, 1.20]	1.35 [1.26, 1.44]

Table 1: Multiplicative coefficients for expected goals and shots on target generated during respective score differentials to project those on the scenario of a tied game with equal number of men, along with 95% confidence intervals.

Red Card Diff	Expected Goals (xG)	Shots On Target
-2	0.52 [0.45, 0.61]	0.52 [0.47, 0.59]
-1	0.65 [0.63, 0.67]	0.68 [0.65, 0.71]
+1	1.85 [1.78, 1.93]	1.77 [1.68, 1.86]
+2	3.08 [2.50, 3.78]	3.06 [2.54, 3.68]

Table 2: Multiplicative coefficients for expected goals and shots on target generated during respective red card differentials to project those on the scenario of a tied game with equal number of men, along with 95% confidence intervals.

One can also witness slight deviations of each respective league from the global effect. For example, English Premier League and German Bundesliga seem to showcase the lowest impact of score differential on offensive outputs, with flatter curves compared to other leagues. Italian Serie A, on the other hand, exhibits the largest drop-off in xG and shots on target as a team goes from trailing to leading in score. The random effects capturing these league-specific deviations were found to be statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

3.2 Statistical Adjustment

Tables 1 and 2 below provide the multiplicative coefficients used for statistical adjustment to project team outputs onto a shared scenario of a tied game played at home at even strength.

Shots and scoring opportunities generated in conducive game circumstances, such as trailing in score or having a man advantage, get penalized via multiplication by a coefficient lower than 1. Conversely, teams that keep producing shots and expected goals despite already leading in score or playing shorthanded, get rewarded via multiplication by coefficients higher than 1. In particular, shots and expected goals generated while down one man are weighed approximately 1.8 times

those produced at even strength, and while down two men - 3 times that.

In Table 1 one can also notice slightly steeper penalties and rewards for generating on-target shot attempts during various score differentials compared to expected goals. Expected goals produced when down in score get penalized by a 10-14% reduction, compared to a 14-17% reduction in shots on target. Expected goals generated when leading in score get rewarded by 10-12%, while shots on target get a 25-32% increase. This aligns with the steeper effect of score differential on shots on target as opposed to expected goals that was discussed back in Section 3.1, Figure 1.

Tables 3 and 4 list the matches where our adjustment procedure produced the most extreme increases and decreases in expected goals (xG) and shots on target. For each game, we also report when the relevant chances occurred, split by whether the team was ahead or behind on the scoreboard, and whether they had more or fewer players on the field. This context helps explain why the adjustments move in the direction they do.

League	Team	Opponent	Season	Total xG		Actual xG (& Minutes Played) When			
				Actual	Adjusted, [95% CI]	Up 1+ goal	Down 1+ goal	Up 1+ man	Down 1+ man
Strongest Positive Shifts in Each League:									
ENG	Aston Villa	Crystal Palace	2020/21	4.5	6.8, [6.5, 7.1]	3.8 (95)*	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (55)
FRA	Toulouse	Nice	2019/20	2.6	5.7, [4.8, 6.7]	0 (0)	2.3 (90)	0 (0)	2.2 (75)*
GER	Bayern Mun	Stuttgart	2020/21	2.4	4.9, [4.5, 5.2]	2.1 (76)*	0 (0)	0 (0)	2.3 (82)
ITA	AS Roma	@ Udinese	2019/20	3.2	6.1, [5.7, 6.5]	2.7 (84)*	0 (0)	0 (0)	2.5 (66)
SPA	Villarreal	Celta	2020/21	3.0	4.9, [4.3, 5.7]	0 (0)	2.7 (76)*	0 (0)	1.3 (56)*
Strongest Negative Shifts in Each League:									
ENG	Man Utd	Southampton	2020/21	4.7	3.0, [2.7, 3.4]	3.9 (80)*	0 (0)	4.7 (97)*	0 (0)
FRA	Bordeaux	Montpellier	2021/22	3.5	1.7, [1.5, 1.9]	0 (0)	3.5 (94)*	3.5 (66)*	0 (0)
GER	RB Leipzig	Stuttgart	2020/21	3.6	2.5, [2.4, 2.7]	2.8 (46)*	0 (0)	3.6 (81)	0 (0)
ITA	Atalanta	Udinese	2019/20	5.7	4.2, [4.0, 4.4]	3.8 (61)*	0.4 (10)	4.5 (65)	0 (0)
SPA	Real Betis	@ Elche	2022/23	4.2	2.6, [2.3, 2.9]	0.2 (3)	1.9 (70)*	3.2 (43)*	0 (0)

Table 3: Individual games across 2017-2023 seasons for each of the five European soccer leagues under consideration where a team experienced strongest positive (first five rows) and strongest negative (last five rows) absolute adjustments in their expected goals (xG). An "@" symbol indicates that the team played away, at the opponent's home field. An asterisk "*" denotes games where the score or red card differential exceeded ± 1 (e.g., ahead by at least 2 goals or down by at least 2 men).

The upward adjustments (top half of each table) are concentrated in games where teams managed to create chances despite playing under conditions that normally depress attacking output—most often while already holding a lead or while down in men. Because our framework

¹ENG: English Premier League; FRA: French Ligue 1; GER: German Bundesliga; ITA: Italian Serie A; SPA: Spanish La Liga.

League	Team	Opponent	Season	Total Shots On Target (SOT)		Actual SOT (& Minutes Played) When			
				Actual	Adjusted	Up 1+ goal	Down 1+ goal	Up 1+ man	Down 1+ man
Strongest Positive Shifts in Each League:									
ENG	Aston Villa	Crystal Palace	2020/21	9	14.9, [14.1, 15.7]	7 (95)*	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (55)
FRA	Paris St-Ger	Toulouse	2017/18	14	21.5, [20.4, 22.7]	7 (61)*	4 (13)	0 (0)	6 (26)
GER	Bayern Mun	Stuttgart	2020/21	7	15.9, [14.7, 17.1]	6 (76)*	0 (0)	0 (0)	7 (82)
ITA	AS Roma	@ Udinese	2019/20	6	13.3, [12.4, 14.2]	5 (84)*	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (66)
SPA	Real Madrid	@ Celta	2019/20	11	19.9, [18.8, 21.1]	10 (88)*	0 (0)	0 (0)	5 (40)
Strongest Negative Shifts in Each League:									
ENG	Wolverhampton	Man City	2019/20	8	4.9, [4.7, 5.2]	0 (6)	6 (65)*	8 (92)	0 (0)
FRA	Bordeaux	Montpellier	2021/22	10	4.6, [4.1, 5.2]	0 (0)	10 (94)*	10 (66)*	0 (0)
GER	Mainz	Hoffenheim	2018/19	12	8.5, [8.1, 8.9]	1 (6)	8 (75)*	9 (59)	0 (0)
ITA	AS Roma	Venezia	2021/22	16	10.4, [9.9, 10.9]	0 (0)	10 (79)	15 (70)	0 (0)
SPA	Las Palmas	Celta	2017/18	11	7.6, [7.1, 8.1]	0 (0)	11 (80)*	6 (43)	0 (0)

Table 4: Individual games across 2017-2023 seasons for each of the five European soccer leagues under consideration where a team experienced strongest positive (first five rows) and strongest negative (last five rows) absolute adjustments in their shots on target (SOT). An "@" symbol indicates that the team played away, at the opponent's home field. An asterisk "*" denotes games where the score or red card differential exceeded ± 1 (e.g., ahead by at least 2 goals or down by at least 2 men).

projects all events onto a baseline state of an even scoreline with equal manpower, numbers accumulated during these circumstances get scaled upward.

A clear illustration comes from Bayern Munich's 2020/21 match against Stuttgart in German Bundesliga. Their raw xG total of 2.4 was boosted to 4.9 (95% CI: [4.5, 5.2]), while their 7 shots on target got scaled up to 15.9 (95% CI: [14.7, 17.1]). Nearly all of their dangerous opportunities came after an early red card left them a man short, yet they still created plenty of chances while leading by at least two goals most of the match.

Similar stories played out for most other matches with a team experiencing a strong positive shift in both Tables 3 and 4, except for Toulouse vs Nice and Villarreal vs Celta in Table 3. Those two matches showcase how playing at a heavy man disadvantage (i.e., down at least 2 men) can result in a notable adjustment even despite the teams trailing most of the game. Toulouse generated 2.3 of their 2.6 expected goals while trailing by one or more goals, but 2.2 of those also came when they were down one **or two** men, resulting in an upwards adjustment from 2.6 to 5.7 (95% CI: [4.8, 6.7]). Analogous scenario held true for Villarreal's fixture against Celta.

The downward shifts (bottom halves of the tables) generally involve sides that accumulated their chances in highly favorable circumstances—trailing on the scoreboard while enjoying a numerical advantage due to opponent's red cards. Because those contexts tend to inflate raw attacking

statistics, our adjustment procedure discounts them when projecting back to the neutral baseline.

Bordeaux's 2021/22 home loss to Montpellier is the starkest example. Their recorded 3.5 xG collapsed to just 1.7 (95% CI: [1.5, 1.9]) after adjustment, while the shots on target got cut down from 10 to 4.6 (95% CI: [4.1, 5.2]). That was due to virtually all of their opportunities having come after gaining a two-man advantage but still chasing the game. The combination of scoreboard deficit and manpower superiority represents the most conducive circumstances for inflated offensive numbers, and our framework corrects for it sharply.

Most other examples of the strongest negative shifts fit the same mold, except for a few matches in Table 3. In particular, Manchester United, RB Leipzig and Atalanta all generated a good chunk of their xG's when actually leading in score, but an even larger portion of their xG's came when down one man (or, in case of Manchester United, even down two men at times). So, even despite the scoring context not being to producing xG's - which tends to resulting in an upward projection by our adjustment mechanism - the man disadvantage still outweighs is, leading to a strong downward projection overall. That reaffirms the higher magnitude of the impact that red card differential has on the offensive production as opposed to the scoring differential, as could be seen back on Figure 1.

Two themes emerge across the adjustments. First, the biggest positive corrections favor teams that sustained pressure while facing constraints—often when leading by multiple goals with fewer players. Second, the largest downward corrections fall on teams that relied heavily on favorable contexts to amass their statistics, such as long stretches with an extra player while already behind. It's important to note that our results highlighted absolute shifts rather than percentage changes, so they naturally emphasize games with relatively high raw totals (e.g., 3+ xG or 10+ shots on target). Teams with smaller totals could experience steep percentage adjustments, but they would not register among the largest absolute movements shown here.

3.3 Forecasting performance comparison

Figure 2 presents the results of the paired t -tests comparing forecasting performance of games' score differentials when using adjusted statistics versus actual values in predicting score differentials for each league-season combination, along with the 95% confidence interval for the average

Figure 2: Paired t -test p -values and 95% confidence intervals for the difference in root mean squared error (RMSE) when predicting final score differentials of future games within each season (individual points) and each league (y-axis) under consideration. Forecasts were generated using linear regression with two explanatory variables: the home and away teams’ statistics (shots or corners) up to the midpoint of the season, either left unchanged (“actual”) or adjusted using our proposed mechanism (“adjusted”).

pairwise difference. It shows a statistically significant improvement overall for both xG (p-value of 0.0231) and shots on target (p-value of 0.0000) at significance level of 0.05, with a larger root mean squared error for actual statistics as opposed to the adjusted ones. Out of 30 league-season pairings (5 leagues, 6 seasons), 22 had an improved performance due to adjustment to xG values, and 25 - due to adjustment to shots on target values.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

This study developed and validated a framework for adjusting soccer performance metrics to account for tactical context, using generalized additive mixed models (GAMMs) applied to minute-level match data from Europe’s top five leagues. By explicitly modeling how score differential, red cards, and home advantage influence offensive production, we derived multiplicative adjustment factors that project observed statistics onto a standardized baseline game state—tied score, even strength, and home venue. This yields more comparable estimates of team quality and attacking efficiency, disentangled from temporary tactical behaviors or match-specific circumstances.

Our findings demonstrate that contextual adjustments meaningfully alter both the interpretation and predictive value of key statistics. Expected goals and shots on target both exhibit strong nonlinear responses to game state: output rises sharply when teams trail or gain a manpower advantage, and declines when leading or playing shorthanded. Applying our adjustments systematically reduced this tactical bias, improving the stability and forecasting accuracy of performance-based models across seasons and leagues. In short, accounting for situational context not only aligns better with intuitive assessments of team strength but also enhances predictive utility in downstream applications such as match outcome modeling or performance benchmarking.

At a conceptual level, this work contributes to the growing body of evidence that game-state awareness is essential in sports analytics. Much like pace- or possession-adjusted statistics in basketball or hockey, context-corrected xG and shot metrics provide a fairer basis for comparison and deeper insight into true team capability.

Future research could extend this framework in several promising directions. First, incorporating richer in-game covariates—such as formation shifts, substitutions, or pressing intensity—may yield even finer-grained contextual adjustments. Second, player-level extensions could uncover how individual shot creation or finishing tendencies evolve under tactical pressure. Third, integrating these adjusted metrics into live win-probability or match simulation models could improve real-time forecasting and decision support. Finally, beyond soccer, the same methodological template can be adapted to other continuous-flow sports (e.g., hockey, rugby, or basketball) where strategic adaptation to game state plays a central role.

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6 Declaration of interest statement

Authors of this work confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest to disclose.

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